

Triterpenoid Constituents of the Stem-bark of *Kopsia fruticosa* A. DC.¹

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The leaves of *Kopsia fruticosa* A. DC., a shrub or a small tree of the family *Apocynaceae*, was investigated previously and has been found to produce a number of indole alkaloids, mainly of aspidosperma type². However, there seems to be no report on the chemical investigation of the stem-bark or root of this plant, so far.

In connection with our studies on Apocynaceæ plants, we undertook a systematic chemical examination of the stem-bark of this plant. Our attempts to isolate any alkaloidal constituent failed. The isolation of several neutral constituents, identified as β amyrin, β -amyrin acetate and γ -sitosterol concerns the subject-matter of the present communication.

Dried and powdered stem-bark (600 g.) of *Kopsia fruticosa* was extracted successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), chloroform and ethanol. The petroleum ether extract on concentration deposited an amorphous solid (A, 6 g.), which was collected by filtration. The filtrate of solid A was separated into basic and neutral fractions. The gummy residue (50 mg.) obtained from the basic fraction giving feeble test for alkaloid with Dragendroff's reagent did not afford any pure substance upon usual processing. The neutral fraction was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. On concentration of the early petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) eluted fractions, a solid residue was obtained. The latter crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture in fine needles (15 mg.), m.p. 235-36°, $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$ (M^+ , m/e 468), $[\alpha]_D^{30} +78^\circ$ (c, 0.45 in $CHCl_3$) showing a single spot on microchromatoplate [R_f 0.5, using silica gel as adsorbent and benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1) as developer]. The compound exhibits positive Liebermann-Burchardt test (pink colour) for triterpene and gives yellow colour with tetranitromethane, indicating the presence of unsaturation. The presence of an acetate function was evident from the appearance of peaks at 5.80 (acetate CO) and 8.03 μ (O-COCH₃) in its IR spectrum (nujol). The mass spectrum of the triterpenoid shows fragmentation pattern characteristic of α - or β -amyrin acetate. The above data suggest its identity with β -amyrin acetate and this has been confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p., IR, and TLC) with an authentic sample of this material. Additional confirmation was received by the hydrolysis of the compound with 5 per cent alcoholic alkali (steam bath, 5 hr.) to yield pure β -amyrin, m.p. 200°.

Subsequent petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) eluted fractions, yielding the same single spot on microchromatoplates, were mixed together and concentrated to yield a white

1. Part V in the series 'Triterpenoids & Related Compounds'. Part IV: S. K. Talapatra, S. Sengupta, Miss S. Banerjee and Mrs. B. Talapatra, *This Journal* (in Press)
2. For a comprehensive review on the alkaloids of *Kopsia* species see B. Gilbert, "Alkaloids", Vol. VIII, edited by Manske, Academic Press, New York, 1965, P. 335.

residue (300 mg.), which crystallised from methanol, m.p. 199-200°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 88^\circ$ (*c.* 0.49 in CHCl_3). Its triterpenoid nature was evident from its pink colouration with Liebermann-Burchardt reagent. It gives a single spot in TLC (R_f 0.5, using silica gel as adsorbent and chloroform as developer). The compound exhibits a peak at 3.04 μ for -OH group in its IR spectrum (nujol). The presence of unsaturation was indicated by the production of yellow colour with tetranitromethane. The triterpene alcohol furnished an acetate, m.p. 238-40°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 77.5^\circ$ (*c.* 0.40 in CHCl_3) showing new peaks at 5.82 and 8.05 μ for acetoxy group, and a benzoate, m.p. 228°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 96^\circ$ (*c.* 0.58 in CHCl_3). The melting points and rotations of the above three compounds correspond to those³ for β -amyrin, β amyrin acetate and β -amyrin benzoate respectively. The identity of the compounds were established by mixed melting point determination (no depression) and superimposable IR spectra with authentic samples in case of β -amyrin and its acetate.

From the benzene eluates of the above chromatogram, a compound (20 mg.), crystallising from ethanol-chloroform in needles, m.p. 149-50°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 42^\circ$ (*c.* 0.53 in CHCl_3) was obtained through rechromatography and several crystallisations. It gave positive Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol and yellow colour with tetranitromethane indicating the presence of unsaturation. It was identified as γ -sitosterol by direct comparison with an authentic material (m.m.p.) and by preparing its acetate m.p. 142°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 40^\circ$ (*c.* 0.35 in CHCl_3) (lit.⁴, $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 45.3^\circ$, m.p. 143-44°).

The solid residue A, m.p. 150-60°, showing only one major spot on micro-chromatoplate, was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. The petroleum ether-benzene (2:1) eluate fractions furnished the major quantity of β amyrin (3 g.), m.p. 199-200° identified through direct comparison with an authentic material (m.m.p., rotation and IR).

The chloroform and ethanol extracts did not afford any pure compound upon usual processing.

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3. Heilbron, Bunbury, Cook and Jones, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Vol. I, Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1953, p. 158.

4. Ref. 3, Vol. 4, p. 362.